

electrode reaction. The effects of Hg-pressure and temperature revealed that i_d increased linearly with $effh^{1/2}$ and the temperature coefficient of i_d is 1.11% per degree. All these observations indicate the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves.

The values of transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^0$) for the electrode reduction of In^{3+} in $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$ have been determined at various concentrations of ligand (0.02–0.10M) and temperatures (25°–45°) by Koutecky's² method as extended by Meites and Israel³. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential and decrease in i_d with increase in $[\text{R}(\text{SH})_2]$ (Table 1) indicate the complex formation between metal ions and the ligand. It may also be observed (Table 1) that the rate of the electrode process increases with temperature and $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards less negative potential supporting the irreversible nature of the waves.

TABLE I

Values of i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn and $K_{f,h}^0$ at various $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$ concentrations and temperatures

$[\text{R}(\text{SH})_2]$ (M)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (volts)	αn	$K_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0.02	11.20	0.658	1.51	0.31×10^{-13}
0.04	11.15	0.665	1.39	1.38×10^{-13}
0.06	11.10	0.672	1.29	4.67×10^{-13}
0.08	11.00	0.678	1.23	9.81×10^{-13}
0.10	10.95	0.684	1.18	14.68×10^{-13}
Temp.(°C)				
25	11.25	0.652	1.548	2.22×10^{-14}
30	11.90	0.628	1.427	6.26×10^{-13}
35	12.60	0.606	1.290	1.53×10^{-11}
40	13.25	0.586	1.231	9.72×10^{-11}
45	14.00	0.566	1.204	3.79×10^{-10}

The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the electrode reaction have been determined⁴ at 25° and found to be 25.48 Kcal/mole, 44.61 Kcal/mole and 64.19 Cal/mole/degree respectively.

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Brucine and *o*-Phenylenediamine Complexes of Blue Perchromate : A Physico-Chemical Study

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COMPLEXES of the blue perchromate with different nitrogenous bases have been studied earlier¹⁻³. Magnetic measurements of red and blue perchromates have been done by Tjabbes², Klemm and Werth¹⁰. Bhatnagar, Prakash and Hamid¹¹ and Tomar, Singh and Singh¹² have measured the magnetic moments of the complexes of the blue perchromate.

In the present communication some new complexes of the blue perchromate with brucine and *o*-phenylenediamine have been prepared and studied.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. Grade. Blue perchromate was prepared by Rai's⁵ method.

Brucine Complex: 50 ml of 1% cold ethereal solution of brucine was added dropwise to 50 ml cold ethereal blue perchromate. A dirty yellow ppt. was formed. After 2–3 hr it was filtered, washed with ether to make the complex free from the base and dried in a desiccator.

***o*-phenylenediamine Complex:** To 50 ml. cold ethereal blue perchromate, an excess of cold and saturated ethereal solution of *o*-phenylenediamine was added. A black ppt. was obtained on keeping the mixture overnight. The ppt. was filtered and washed with ether till the filtrate was colourless. It was then dried in a desiccator.

Determination of oxidising powers of the complexes: Definite weights of the complexes were dissolved separately in the minimum volume of 1N NaOH solution and the solution was made upto a definite volume with distilled water. Oxidising powers of the complexes were determined volumetrically as suggested by Tomar, Singh and Singh¹².

Estimation of Chromium in the basic part and determination of the oxidising powers of the filtrate: Chromium in the basic part of the complexes was estimated (i) volumetrically, and (ii) gravimetrically as described by Tomar, Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*). Oxidising power of the filtrate (obtained from the gravimetric method) was also determined by the method suggested by the above workers. The observations and the results have been given in Table I.

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NOTES

TABLE 1—BRUCINE AND *o*-PHENYLENEDIAMINE COMPLEXES OF BLUE PERCHROMATE

(Z) 0.2299 g of the brucine complex dissolved in *N* NaOH solution and the solution made upto 250 ml.

(Z) 0.2919 g of the *o*-phenylenediamine complex dissolved in *N* NaOH solution and the solution made upto 250 ml.

Complexes	Volume (ml.) of hypo solution used in titrating 25 ml of			After precipitation of Cr(OH) ₃ from (d), % of Cr in basic part	% of Total Cr. (Gravimetrically)	Ratios			
	(Z) solution without oxidation	(Z) solution after oxidation	Filtrate of (Z) solution after pptions of Cr(OH) ₃			c/b	c/d	d/b	f/e
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j
1. Brucine	3.70	7.30	3.65	4.999	10.021	1.97	2.00	0.98	2.00
	3.75	7.35	3.70	4.990	10.001	1.96	1.98	0.98	2.00
2. <i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	2.20	4.50	2.30	10.800	21.556	2.04	1.95	1.04	1.99
	2.20	4.70	2.30	10.802	21.500	2.13	2.04	1.04	1.99

Estimation of the elements : The estimation of the elements (Chromium, Nitrogen, Carbon, Hydrogen and Oxygen) was done as reported earlier⁸.

Magnetic susceptibility measurement : Molar magnetic susceptibilities (K_m) of these complexes were determined by Gouy's method at room temperature. The magnetic moment values for brucine and *o*-phenylenediamine complexes were found to be 3.848 B.M. and 3.701 B.M. respectively.

Infra-red studies : Infra-red spectra of the complexes were obtained on Perkin Elmer Model 521 (4000 cm^{-1} to 250 cm^{-1}). The observations and results have been recorded in Table 2.

Discussion

The chemical and analytical studies of the complexes alongwith their magnetic moments and I.R. examination clearly show that (i) both complexes contain equal amounts of chromium in acidic and basic parts, (ii) the base molecule is attached to the blue perchromate molecule in both complexes, (iii) the probable molecular formula for both complexes can be written as $R_2Cr_1(CrO_{10})_3$ where R stands for one molecule of the base, and (iv) the magnetic moment data support the presence of Cr(III).

The possibility of attachment of the base molecule seems quite probable in the formula $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_3$ as it has the necessary Cr(III) for complex formation.

TABLE 2—I.R. SPECTRA OF COMPLEXES

Intensity of bands : s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, v.w. = very weak, b = broad.

Name of the complex	S. No.	Prominent and characteristic peaks in pure base (cm^{-1})	Prominent and characteristic peaks in the complex (cm^{-1})	Vibration indications
Brucine Complex.	1.	760 (w.b.)	765 (w.b.)	Ortho disubstitution of methoxy group.
	2.	—	875 (w)	O-O stretching.
	3.	1030 (v.w.)	1040 (v.w.)	Ether linkages.
	4.	—	1120 (b)	C-O stretching.
	5.	1275 (b)	1290 (s)	C-N stretching.
	6.	1450 (m)	1460 (m)	CH ₂ deformations.
	7.	1625 (s)	—	C=C (aromatic) stretching.
	8.	1660 (s)	1650 (s)	C=O stretching.
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine Complex.	1.	740 (s)	750 (s)	Ortho disubstitution (of amino groups in benzene ring).
	2.	—	860 (v.w.)	O-O stretching.
	3.	1270 (s)	—	C-N (aromatic) stretching.
	4.	1590 (m)	1550 (b)	C=C (aromatic) stretching.
	5.	3380 (s)	3350 (b)	NH ₂ stretching (showing the presence of amino groups).

The results were interpreted on the basis of available literature¹³⁻¹⁶.

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Triazene-1-oxides. Part I. Cobalt(II) Mixed Chelates containing Triazene-1-oxide and Dipyriddy (or o-phenanthroline)

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SIGNIFICANT studies on the structures of square planar nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of triazene-1-oxides¹(I), formerly designated as 3-hydroxytriazenes²(II), have recently been done by Chakravorty *et al.*³. Tendency of adduct formation in pyridine is more pronounced in cobalt(II) (solution magnetic moment ~ 4.4 B.M.) than in nickel(II).

We report in this note some cobalt(II) pseudo octahedral complexes containing two triazene-1-oxide moieties and one dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline.

Experimental

The ligands were obtained following published procedures⁴.

General Method of syntheses of the mixed chelates: To an alcoholic (30 ml) solution of the ligand TH (X = H) (.002 mole) was added a solution of cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate (.001 mole in 30 ml 1:1 aqueous ethanol). The bis(triazene-1-oxide) cobalt(II) complex was filtered, suspended in hot acetone (25 ml) and treated with dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline (.001 mole). The chocolate brown solution was filtered and the filtrate allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator. The deep chocolate brown crystals were of analytical purity but could be recrystallised from minimum volume of hot acetone. In the case of the nitroderivatives, the ligands (.002 mole) were dissolved in a greater volume of alcohol (~ 180 ml).

Estimation of cobalt and nitrogen and determination of conductance and magnetic moments were done as usual. Molecular weights were measured cryoscopically in benzene. Depressions being small (being limited by solubility of the complexes in benzene), the molecular weight values have a precision⁵ of $\pm 20\%$ of the calculated ones.

Relevant data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussions

The square planar bis(ligand) cobalt(II) complexes react readily with the N-N donor heterocycles, dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline to produce the mixed chelates $[\text{CoT}_2\text{dipy}]$ or $[\text{CoT}_2\text{o-phen}]$. The complexes are generally soluble in acetone, benzene, chloroform but less so in ethanol. The complexes are non-electrolytes, Λ_m in acetone⁶ being $\sim 1-26$ ohms⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹. Within limits of error ($\pm 20\%$) the complexes are also monomeric in freezing benzene. Since the 4-coordinated $[\text{CoT}_2]$ complexes were low spin square planar ($\mu \sim 2.1$ B.M.) it was fascinating to examine if the presence of the strong field dipyriddy or o-phenanthroline in the mixed chelates could produce low-spin pseudo-octahedral complexes. The